

WATER RESOURCES - FOR THE FUTURE

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Annotation: The article underscores the vital importance of water resources, stressing their role in sustaining life and the urgency of addressing global water scarcity. It highlights international efforts, particularly led by the UN, and Uzbekistan's proactive stance in Central Asian water management. Emphasising the country's strategic approach, it outlines initiatives to promote water-saving technologies and digital solutions. Despite progress, challenges persist, necessitating ongoing modernization. Ultimately, Uzbekistan's water policy remains focused on sustainable solutions for crucial societal challenges.

Keywords: Water scarcity, Sustainable development goals, Integrated water resources management, UN World Water Development Report, Water diplomacy, Central Asian glaciers International cooperation, Water-saving technologies.

Water is the most abundant substance on Earth. We cannot survive without water and even mild dehydration can have serious consequences. Drinking water can help increase satiety and reduce calorie intake. Importance of Water to Humans:

- Comprises 55-78% of the human body: Water is the primary component of all cells and tissues, and is involved in every bodily function.
- Hydrates cells and tissues: Water helps maintain the structure and function of cells, and prevents dehydration.
- Transports nutrients and oxygen: Water carries essential nutrients and oxygen to cells throughout the body.

- Regulates body temperature: Sweating helps cool the body down, while shivering helps generate heat.
- Lubricates joints and tissues: Water helps lubricate joints, reducing friction and pain.
- Removes waste products: Water helps flush out waste products from the body through urine and faeces. However, 97.5% of the hydrosphere is in salt water and only 2.5% is in fresh water.

From year to year, the world's fresh water reserves are rapidly depleting, and its consumption is constantly growing. According to the UN, water scarcity currently affects more than 40% of the world's people. It is predicted that if nothing is done, then by the middle of the 21st century the number of people living with constant water shortages will exceed 4 billion people. In this regard, the world community, in order to achieve sustainable development goals, is implementing measures in the field of integrated water resources management and promoting water-saving projects and programs. At the same time, the UN World Water Development Report for 2023 focuses on partnership and cooperation of countries in this issue, the problem is considered in the context of the dominant “agriculture”, “environment”, “human settlements”, “industry”, “health” " and "climate change".

In March this year, a truly historic conference on water resources took place at the UN headquarters. The goal is to further mobilise the efforts of states to achieve voluntary and internationally agreed water-related goals and targets by 2030.

UN Secretary-General António Guterres emphasised: “Water is a human right and a common denominator of development to shape a better future. However, a disastrous situation has developed in the field of water resources.” According to him, people consume water “vampirically,” and global warming leads to its evaporation, which, in turn, causes disruption of the water cycle, destruction of ecosystems and contamination of groundwater.”

Uzbekistan is an important partner in solving water problems in Central Asia.

According to experts, Central Asian glaciers, which are the main source of water

for the region's rivers, lose on average 0.6-0.8% of their glaciated area and 0.1% of their volume per year. The current situation requires taking urgent measures to adapt to sudden climate changes.

The leadership of our country carries out coordinated actions with neighbouring countries within the framework of constructive cooperation in water issues. At the same time, a significant element of this process is the introduction of integrated water resources management at the regional and national levels.

The waterways and water resources of the countries in the region are closely interconnected. Therefore, it is impossible to do without "water diplomacy". There is no alternative to solving the water problem that takes into account equally the interests of the countries and peoples of the region.

As a result of the pragmatic policy pursued in recent years, trusting relationships have been established between the countries of the region, which have become the basis for the effective use of transboundary water resources.

Uzbekistan is consistently developing cooperation with the Central Asian states on water issues within the framework of the International Fund for Saving the Aral Sea (IFAS), the Interstate Coordination Water Commission (ICWC), and in intergovernmental working groups on water use. In recent years, as a result of agreements concluded through mutually beneficial cooperation with Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan and Turkmenistan, positive results have been achieved in the field of water supply in the Syr Darya and Amu Darya river basins.

In order to increase the efficiency of use of water resources, stable water supply to the population and all sectors of the economy, improve the reclamation of irrigated lands, widespread introduction of market mechanisms and digital technologies in the water sector, the Concept for the development of the water sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan was approved

2020–2030, the Strategy for Water Resources Management and Development of the Irrigation Sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2021–2023.

Based on these documents, work on the introduction of water-saving technologies continues consistently. Activities started in previous years are producing results through the provision of subsidies and benefits by the state. Today, the coverage of water-saving irrigation technologies has reached 25% of all irrigated areas.

It should be noted that the republic attaches great importance to increasing the number of local enterprises producing equipment and components of water-saving technologies. If before

In 2019, there were only three such local enterprises, but currently there are already about 50.

To maintain accurate accounting and reporting of water consumption, create conditions for fair and transparent distribution between consumers in the water sector, modern digital technologies are being introduced, including Smart Water, reclamation observation wells for monitoring groundwater levels, and online monitoring installations. at pumping stations to control water consumption, etc.

However, as part of the modernization of water management facilities, the introduction of digital technologies, and modern management methods, much remains to be done. As they say, the one who walks can master the road. One thing is undeniable - the water policy pursued by Uzbekistan is focused on wisely solving vital problems with a focus on the future.